

THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA AND IDEOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205493>

Annotation. In this study, on the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the forms of manifestation of the globalization process, its specific aspects, the work being carried out on the issue of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism in the conditions of globalization, the need and conditions for protecting the youth of Uzbekistan from ideas that do not correspond to their national mentality have been analyzed. During the analysis, the work of foreign researchers in this regard was commented. In the study, proposals and recommendations, scientific conclusions related to the education of young people in the spirit of patriotism and not giving in to foreign ideas are presented on the example of Uzbekistan in the context of globalization.

Key words: globalization consciousness, culture, pedagogy, comprehensive approach, comparative comparison, observation, expert assessment, analysis and synthesis.

At the current stage of its development, the complex nature of the development of the society, the appearance of its negative consequences along with the positive aspects of the development, poses new problems to humanity. Today, it is impossible to find any region or country that is completely protected from interactions. It is directly related to globalization and integration processes. The process of globalization takes place differently depending on the potential of countries in the economic, political, military, spiritual, and religious spheres. Observing this process as a relatively more active phenomenon in developed countries shows that it is a phenomenon related to the development of society. In order to reduce the negative impact and increase the positive impact of the current globalization process on the countries of the world, it is necessary to deeply understand the nature of this phenomenon and study its features. A deep study of the nature and characteristics of globalization creates an opportunity to adapt to it, to change its directions as needed, to use its power "against itself". It is clear from this that the development of methods, tools and mechanisms of positive and creative use of the globalization process on a scientific basis is one of the urgent problems of today. The term globalization was first used in the field of finance and economics in 1981. But the full description and meaning of

this term was revealed by the American scientist Charles Taz Russell in the middle of 1990. In general, this concept has been given various explanations and definitions in the scientific literature.

In today's process of globalization, the concepts of homeland and patriotism, nation and nationalism are becoming more important than ever. New problems related to preservation of identity, protection from foreign influences, protection from ideological and ideological attacks appeared for each society. In such conditions, increasing the ideological immunity of young people and protecting them from falling under the influence of foreign ideologies is one of the most urgent issues. In such circumstances, the most important condition for protecting the spirituality of young people from destructive ideological attacks is the formation of ideological immunity in them. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, this is evident in the practical implementation of the following tasks:

- raising the youth in the spirit of national ideals and loyalty to the Motherland, instilling in their hearts and minds that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty;
- to be proud of our ancient history and culture, our national heroes who selflessly fought for the independence and prosperity of our beloved Motherland, to form a sense of being worthy of them, to strengthen confidence in the power and potential of our national army;
- to strengthen the understanding that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as the theoretical and practical skills in this regard;
- forming in young people the skills of approaching the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity against various internal and external threats;
- educating young people with the ability to make quick and independent decisions in any complex situations, to effectively use modern military equipment;
- To be ready to protect the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military field, but also in all aspects of life, to be selfless for the country - to inculcate in the minds of young people through real examples and effective means that this is the demand of today. [5]

Globalization is such a process that a passive society always loses. In this process, it is impossible to remain in the position of an observer or protection from foreign ideas and influences. Maybe we need to respond to the foreign and even destructive ideas entering our society by different ways and means by promoting our national idea, ideology, values and traditions, rich cultural

heritage, and lifestyle to the world community. After all, the achievements of the great scientists who grew up in Uzbekistan in the fields of science, religion, art and military have had a great impact on the spirituality of the whole world for centuries. The development of the philosophy of Abu Nasr Farabi, the development of the world science of Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Zamakhshari, Khorezmi, Mirza Ulughbek, the hadith, kalam, fiqh sciences and mysticism of Ismail Bukhari, at Termizi, Moturidi, Abdukhaliq Ghijduvani, Bahavuddin Naqshbandi, Ahmad Yassavi The universal contributions of Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Mirza Babur to the development of military art, the views of enlightened artists such as Abdurauf Fitrat, Cholpon, Abdulla Qadiri on the independence of the state are recognized by the whole world. Therefore, our society has been not only a consumer of spiritual and educational, ideological and ideological updates of the world, but has been among the pioneers and creators of these processes. Henry Bergson, Karl Popper, George Soros and others, supporters of the "Open Society" theory, which arose in the Western world, explain their views with the priority of personal benefits. At the root of this lies the self-interest and egoism that is the basis of Western philosophy. But the Eastern way of life favors more community and harmony. Public control over education is strong in our society. Public control cultivates feelings such as shame, concern, respect, and respect, which protect people from the abyss and encourage them to live according to universally recognized standards. In fact, the family and neighborhood as a democratic institution in the East have an important place in the education of young people. The importance of this institution in forming a healthy spiritual and moral environment in the society is undeniable. In raising young people to be patriotic, loyal to national traditions and values, it is necessary to consistently continue the work carried out in the family and neighborhood, to look at the issue of education as an issue at the level of society and state policy. Uzbek enlightener Abdurauf Fitrat states in his pamphlet "Family" that "Whoever brings up naughty children does not serve humanity, but acts as an enemy." Since the issue of education of a well-rounded generation in the society is the object of study of such sciences as philosophy, social studies, pedagogy, literature, we should not forget that the basis of this issue is moral integrity. After all, only morally perfect, patriotic and broad-minded people can have a conscious attitude to the processes in society. Because in the current era, when threats to our moral principles are increasing, moral integrity is seen as a means of protection against inevitable decline. [7]

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